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Fostering Bright Smile: An Exploration of Oral Health Factors Affecting the Role of Parents of Preschoolers

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Abstract

This study determined the oral health factors affecting preschoolers and the role of parents in prevention. Particularly, it focused to all the 23 Child Care Development Centers in San Manuel, Pangasinan. The study used descriptive method of research and included 230 parents from 23 centers as respondents. It used percentage, frequency counts, weighted mean, and Pearson r product moment coefficient of correlation through SPSS 26 in its statistical treatment. Further, the study found out that respondent-parents are predominantly females, 185 or 80.4 percent, 106 or 46.1 percent belong to ages 20-21, 183 or 79.6 percent are Roman Catholic. They are mostly married, 169 or 73.5 percent, high school graduate with 155 of them or 67.4 percent, and 205 of them or 89.1 percent are housewife or househusband. Majority of the respondents have 5,000 and below income, there are 166 of them or 72.2 percent. They belong to a nuclear type of family, 184 of them or 80 percent, and have 4-5 members in the family. The respondents agree that the dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, education and awareness, and collaboration with healthcare providers are oral health factors highly affecting preschoolers. Further, respondents neither agree nor disagree that the parental attitudes and beliefs, and cultural influences are oral health factors affecting preschoolers. There is a significant relationship between the factors affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children and the respondents' profile variables. Particularly between the factors on dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, parental attitudes and beliefs, cultural influences, and education and awareness, and the profile variables, sex, age, highest educational attainment, income, and number of family members.

Keywords: *oral health, preschoolers, oral hygiene, dietary habits*

Introduction

A bright smile starts with a blooming face and a beautiful set of pearly white teeth. To have such, it should come from an excellent oral and dental health hygiene. Oral and dental health is an integral part of complete health and well-being (Hafez, 2017). Oral health is a state of the mouth, teeth and a facial structure that enables individuals to perform essential functions such as eating, breathing and speaking, and encompasses psychological dimensions such as self-confidence, well-being and the ability to socialize, work without pain, discomfort and embarrassment (WHO, 2023)

According to the World Health Organization health status report of 2022, they have estimated that oral diseases affect close to 3.5 billion people worldwide, with three out of four people suffer from caries of permanent teeth and 514 million children suffer from caries of primary teeth. In the Philippines, according to the National Oral Health Survey, the prevalence of oral diseases such as untreated caries of deciduous teeth in children 1 to 9 years old is 45%, untreated caries of permanent teeth is 29.4%, severe periodontal disease in people 15 years old and older is 3.2%, and edentulous in people 20 years old and older is 7.5% (WHO, 2022) Further, data from the National Monitoring and Evaluation for Dental Survey (NMEDS) indicates that 87.4% of Filipinos suffer from tooth decay or dental cavities. Further, a national health survey revealed that 97% of 6-year old children had dental caries with a mean of 8.4 affected teeth, and 85% had odontogenic infection (Monse et al., 2015).

Everyone has a role to perform to improve the oral health of children. It is not a role exclusively for parents regardless of whatever situation may be. As such, to ensure the maintenance of good oral health among learners and personnel during the pandemic, the Department of Education released DepEd Order No. 041, or the Guidelines on the Implementation of School Dental Health Program (SDHCP) including the Medical and Nursing Services for SY 2020-2021. The program aims to provide access to health services that need preventive and curative services including immediate dental and medical emergency care in schools by establishing fully functional clinics. All activities in the policy that require the physical presence of learners in school premises are subject to the conditions of partial or full-scale face-to-face classes. The beneficiary school clinics are given dental equipment with dental and medical supplies and referral delivery network with the rural health units (www.deped.gov.ph)

Habits and practices are important factors that could affect one's perception and action towards dental health care. In the study of Fernandez et al. (2021), in general the children reported positive behaviors regarding dental habits and oral hygiene practices. Children's opinions and beliefs about the dentist were also globally positive, however the results suggested that younger children reported more positive attitudes, emotions and previous experiences. Prevalence of dental fear and anxiety is also recognized that impact the children's future dental behavior in particular on uncooperativeness or even prolonged avoidance of dental treatment that exacerbates problems related to one's oral health.

It was concluded in the study of Ceylan et al. (2022), the dietary habits, anthropometric measurements, oral and dental health practices, gender, and socioeconomic status were shown to be effective on caries. Caries risk assessment and determining leading risk factors

enable effective prevention programs to be implemented at different levels. As it was found out in the study that 70.9 % of the respondent children have dental caries on their permanent teeth. The number of girls with caries in permanent teeth and boys with caries in milk teeth was higher. The frequency of seeing a dentist and changing toothbrush vary according to the socioeconomic status. Also, there is a negative correlation between oral and dental health indicators and anthropometric measurements.

Another study that may be considered significant is the study of Alas et al. (2023) on the exploration of socio-economics and its role in the oral health care of patients in a Philippine government hospital. Findings show that people's use of healthcare services is influenced by predisposing, enabling, and need related factors. The knowledge of and observance of good oral health is essential in determining the need for oral healthcare. Moreover, a variety of socioeconomic and personal factors (enabling and predisposing) are crucial in facilitating or impeding people's ability to access and make use of oral healthcare services.

It shows in the study of Alfaro (2017) that social behavioral risk factors have significant roles in the experience of dental caries in both children and adults. Among school children aged 6 to 12 years old, they have found prevalence of caries to be at 92.3%. Children who grew up plagued with dental caries and who have family members with serious dental caries are more likely to be at risk of having dental caries in the future. This result was mostly attributed to some public measures including limited to no access of dental care, lack of accessible preventive measures such as water fluoridation, supplementation of fluoride, and pit and fissure sealants and the lack of information on the importance of self-care practices and oral well-being.

Consequently, dental health habits introduced by parents as early as preschoolers can provide a clear view of what children can sustain as they grow older. In the study of Maderazo et al. (2014) shows that a good oral health habits in childhood often takes place with parents especially with mothers. Since parents are primary social force influencing child development in the early childhood years, it seems that interventions targeting parental oral health beliefs and practices play beneficial roles in the intervention of oral health problems such as dental caries. Maternal influence to dental health status was found that maternal age, maternal education, location of residence, maternal knowledge and attitudes were positively correlated to the child caries and oral hygiene status. Results of the study also shown some reasons associated to the development of dental fear among children were personal experiences like irregular dental visits, dental settings, dental procedures (injection and aesthetic concern), and influence of peers and parents.

The study of Mendoza et al. (2020) on examining the oral health of Filipinos, issues were highlighted such as: a) health service delivery needs strong collaboration of LGUs; b) insufficient workforce of dental professionals; c) market availability of sufficiently fluoridated toothpaste per age group; and d) health financing scheme on oral health services. If we are to dig deeper to these results, these only shows that policies must be enhanced and developed to better address the oral health concerns not only in small communities but in the whole country at large. As such policy making bodies must see to it that at least they could pass a law, a program or any implementing guidelines to strengthen and widen the dental health programs. Further, there study concluded that with the shift in the health system landscape brought by the UHC Act, timely and responsive inter-sectoral interventions, focusing on prevention, must be set to attain the target decrease in the prevalence of dental caries. It was also recommended to engage the academe and training institutions to increase the workforce, consider international standards on sugar consumption as appropriate, and ensure sufficient funds for sustainability of oral health programs, particularly school-based caries prevention programs starting in preschools.

With all the cited ideas, concepts and findings, this study will look into the oral health factors affecting preschoolers and the role of parents in prevention. Particularly, it will focus into the profile of parents and the specific factors affecting the oral health practices of parents. This study will discern significant relationships between and among the respondents' profile variables and the factors affecting the oral health of preschoolers included in this study.

Research Questions

This study focused on the oral health factors affecting preschoolers and the role of parents in prevention. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. religion;
 - 1.4. marital status;
 - 1.5. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.6. occupation;
 - 1.7. family monthly income;
 - 1.8. family type; and
 - 1.9. number of family members?
2. What is the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschoolers along:
 - 2.1. dental health knowledge;
 - 2.2. dietary habits;
 - 2.3. access to dental health;

- 2.4. parental attitudes and beliefs;
 - 2.5. cultural influences;
 - 2.6. educational awareness; and
 - 2.7. collaboration of healthcare providers?
3. Is there significant relationship between the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschoolers and their profile variables?
 4. What program can be recommended to improve and enhance the oral health practices among parents of preschoolers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive method of research. According to Wasll (2015), descriptive research is a formal, objective, systematic process to describe and test relationships and examine cause and effect interactions among variables. Surveys were utilized for descriptive, explanatory, and exploratory research. Moreover, a survey is utilized to collect original data for describing a population too large to directly observe. A survey obtains information from a sample of people using self-report, that is, the people respond to a series of questions posed by the investigator (Frey et al., 2014).

According to Trochim (2015), descriptive research methods are those that seek to objectively measure the variables of interest. To qualify and quantify the effects of learner's perception on behavioral choices, this study offers a guide to the data collection and analysis, which provides useful information that is relevant to pre-service and practicing this research, a structured questionnaire was selected as a research tool.

Furthermore, Groves et al. (2015) explained the fact that questionnaires are utilized by researchers to convert information directly given by people into data. The findings suggest that classroom management has an impact on how learners learn and how educators manage to learn in a classroom situation.

In this study, the information was collected through self-administered questionnaires distributed digitally or personally to the respondents by the researcher. The research instrument is a questionnaire which was used to gather information from the respondents. Likewise, quantitative research techniques using the Likert scale was utilized.

Respondents

Respondents of the study were the parents of preschoolers of child development centers in the municipality of San Manuel, Pangasinan. There are 23 Child Development Centers. Purposively, all the Child Development Centers was included in this study and 10 parents in each Child Development Center served as respondents of this study. The researcher see it fit that all the child development centers represented the total population. Most especially, the researcher served as dentist in these centers. As such, a total of 230 parents served as the respondents coming from all the barangay child development centers in San Manuel, Pangasinan.

Instruments

In this study, the information was collected through self-administered questionnaires distributed personally to the respondents by the researcher. The research instrument is a questionnaire which intended to gather information from the respondents. Likewise, quantitative research techniques using the Likert scale were utilized.

A survey questionnaire was utilized as the primary tool for gathering the needed data. The initial draft was prepared by the researcher and for review by the adviser or research panel. The survey questionnaire for the respondents consisted of the following parts. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part I dealt with the profile of the respondents including sex, age, marital status, religion, highest educational attainment, occupation, monthly family income, family type, and number of family members. Part II dealt with the factors affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. This included dental health knowledge, oral hygiene practices, dietary habits, access to dental health, parental attitudes and beliefs, cultural influences, education awareness, and collaboration with healthcare providers.

To obtain the reliability and validity of the survey questionnaire, the researcher asked the help of validators. The set of validators included the research adviser, a research expert, and a Child Care Worker in the municipality of San Manuel, Pangasinan. Cronbach's alpha was utilized to measure the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire. The computed Cronbach alpha reliability of 0.94 implied that the instrument that was utilized in this study is 94% reliable. The reliability coefficient was calculated using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient formula. The correlation coefficient of 0.75 was considered adequate to judge the reliability of the instrument.

In addition, data collection started by applying for a research permit from the authorities' concern. The researcher administered the questionnaires in cooperation with the Child Care workers and parents, and discussed the guidelines on how to give the response to the questionnaires. Once the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, the researcher retrieved them immediately or for not later than one week. Results were recorded and were statistically treated.

Procedure

The implementation of the study was undertaken by the researcher after permission is secured from the proper authorities concern in San Manuel, Pangasinan. Proper communication was coordinated to the Child Care Workers before the distribution of questionnaire. The researcher oriented the respondent-parents which was either done verbally or as text information before the distribution of questionnaire. The conduct of the study helped parents deal with the oral health care of their children.

Further, the researcher retrieved the same questionnaire and the responses. The purpose and objectives of the study were clearly explained. Utmost confidentiality was assured to avoid inhibitions from the respondents in accomplishing the questionnaire. The respondents were asked to choose their preferred response by checking the appropriate space or box.

Data Analysis

The data that were gathered from the questionnaire were subjected to appropriate tools to answer the specific problems of the study. The data were tallied, organized, tabulated, and presented in textual and tabular form.

Frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents

The weighted mean was used to determine the factors affecting oral health of preschoolers and the role of parents in prevention. The following scale/legend was used to interpret and analyze the data to be gathered.

Scale	Limits	Descriptive Equivalent	Description
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon)	The factor very highly affects the oral health practices among parents of preschool children
4	3.50-4.49	Agree (Umaayon)	The factor highly affects the oral health practices among parents among parents of preschool children
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon)	The factor moderately affects the oral health practices among parents among parents of preschool children
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree (Di ummayon)	The factor slightly affects the oral health practices among parents among parents of preschool children
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)	The factor does not affect the oral health practices among parents among parents of preschool children

Pearson r Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to determine significant relationship between the factors affecting oral health of preschoolers and the selected profile variables.

The data of the study were processed, organized, and summarize through the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 26). The data were summarized, analyzed, and interpreted in terms of frequencies, ranking, percent, and measures of central tendencies and variability. The researcher attempted to be more comprehensive, qualitative and critical in the analysis.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the data collected, statistical analyses made, and the interpretation of the salient findings. The result of the analyses of the data were organized in tabular form and sequenced in the order of the specific research problems that they are intended to answer.

Profile of Respondents

Tables 1.1 and 1.2 show the data on the profile variables sex, age, religion, marital status, highest educational attainment, occupation, family monthly income, family type, and number of family members.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents across the Variables Sex, Age, Religion, Marital Status, and Highest Educational Attainment

Table 1.1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' profile across the variables: sex, age, religion, marital status, and highest educational attainment.

Sex. The respondent-parents are predominantly females. There are 185 females or 80.4 percent and 45 males or 19.6 percent.

This is a typical situation among parents in the preschool which is mostly dominated by females but at least somehow, there are those male parents who manage to take care of their children and accompany them to school. This can be easily seen in the obvious difference in the number of male parents against female parents.

Age. Most of the respondent-parents, 106 of them or 46.1 percent belong to ages 20-21. It is followed by 78 or 33.9 percent of them under ages 22-23. Forty-four (44) or 19.1 percent of them belong to the 24 and above age bracket, and only 2 or 0.9 percent belong to ages 19 and below.

Religion. Majority of the respondent-parents, 183 of them of 79.6 percent are Roman Catholic. It is followed by 26 or 11.3 percent who are Born Again Christians. Only 6 or 2.6 percent belong to the Iglesia ni Cristo. There are 15 parents or 6.5 percent of them who belong to different religions or beliefs.

This result proves that majority of our community still believe in the Catholic faith.

Marital Status. The respondent-parents are mostly married. There are 169 or 73.5 percent of them who are married. It is followed by 34 parents or 14.8 percent of them have a live-in status. Twenty-seven (27) or 11.7 percent of the parents have a single status.

Highest Educational Attainment. Majority of the respondents are high school graduate. There are 155 or 67.4 percent of them who are high school graduate. It is followed by 44 or 19.1 percent college graduates. Tie at 22 or 5.2 percent are parents who are elementary graduates and vocational graduates. There are only 7 or 3.0 percent who have reached post-graduate.

Table 1.1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents across the Variables Sex, Age, Religion, Marital Status, and Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Variable Category	Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	45	19.6
	Female	185	80.4
	Total	230	100.0
Age	19 & below	2	0.9
	20-21	106	46.1
	22-23	78	33.9
	24 & above	44	19.1
	Total	230	100.0
Religion	Roman Catholic	183	79.6
	Iglesia ni Cristo	6	2.6
	Born Again	26	11.3
	Others	15	6.5
	Total	230	100.0
Marital Status	Single	27	11.7
	Married	169	73.5
	Live-in	34	14.8
	Total	230	100.0
Highest Educational Attainment	Elementary Graduate	12	5.2
	High School Graduate	155	67.4
	Vocational Graduate	12	5.2
	College Graduate	44	19.1
	Post Graduate	7	3.0
	Total	230	100.0

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents across the Variables Occupation, Monthly Family Income, Family Type, and Number of Family Members

Table 1.2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents’ profile across the variables: occupation, monthly family income, family type, and number of family members.

Occupation. Majority of the respondent-parents, 205 of them or 89.1 percent are housewife or househusband. There are 7 parents or 3.0 percent who worked as cook or chef, and 2 or 0.9 percent as teachers. There are 16 of them or 7.0 percent who have different occupations.

Monthly Family Income. Majority of the respondent-parents have 5,000 and below income, there are 166 of them or 72.2 percent. It is followed by 23 parents or 10 percent who have 10,001-15,000 pesos income. There are 19 or 8.3 percent who have 20,001 and above pesos income, and 12 or 5.2 percent with 5,001-10,000 pesos income. Only 10 of them or 4.3 percent who have 15,001-20,000 pesos income.

Family Type. Majority of the respondent-parents have a nuclear type of family, 184 of them or 80 percent. It is followed by 36 parents or 15.7 percent with extended family. Only 10 or 4.3 percent are single parents.

Number of Family Members. Majority of the respondents have 4-5 members in the family, 140 of them or 60.9 percent. It is followed by 72 parents or 31.3 percent with 2-3 members. Only 18 or 7.8 percent have 6-8 members.

Table 1.2 *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents across the Variables Occupation, Monthly Family Income, Family Type, and Number of Family Members*

Variable	Variable Category	Frequency	Percent
Occupation	Housewife/Househusband	205	89.1
	Teacher	2	0.9
	Cook/Chef	7	3.0
	Others	16	7.0
	Total	230	100.0
Monthly Family Income	5,000 pesos & below	166	72.2
	5001 – 10,000 pesos	12	5.2
	10,001- 15,000 pesos	23	10.0
	15,001 – 20,000 pesos	10	4.3
	20,001 & above pesos	19	8.3
Total	230	100.0	
Family Type	Nuclear Family	184	80.0
	Extended Family	36	15.7
	Single Parent	4	1.7
	Others	6	2.6
Total	230	100.0	
Number of Family Members	2 - 3 members	72	31.3
	4 - 5 members	140	60.9
	6 - 8 members	18	7.8
Total	230	100.0	

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children

Tables 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 show the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschool children.

Table 2 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along dental health knowledge.

Table 2. *Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Dental Health Knowledge*

Indicator Statements	Mean	Interpretation
<i>A. Dental Health Knowledge</i>		
1. I know the best time to brush my teeth is to wait at least 30 minutes after eating (Alam ko na ang pinakamagandang oras para magsipilyo ay di bababa sa 30 minuto pagkatapos kumain)	3.92	Agree
2. I know that daily flossing helps to get rid of bacteria and food caught in between my teeth (Alam ko na ang araw-araw na flossing ay nakakatulong upang maalis ang bacteria at pagkain na nasa pagitan ng aking mga ngipin)	4.13	Agree
3. I know that applying fluoride to my teeth preserves the minerals and guards against cavities. (Alam ko na ang paglalagay ng fluoride sa aking mga ngipin ay nagpapanatili ng mga mineral at nagbabantay laban sa pagkabulok ng ngipin)	4.28	Agree
4. I know that I need to visit the dentist for check-up at least once a year. (Alam ko na kailangan kong bumisita at magpakonsulta sa dentista kahit isang beses sa isang taon)	3.65	Agree
5. I know that wearing bite splints is necessary when I grind my teeth while sleeping. (Alam ko na ang pagsusuot ng “bite splints” ay kailangan kapag naggagasgasan ang aking mga ngipin sa aking pagtulog)	3.53	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean 3.904		Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents agree that the dental health knowledge is a factor affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. The data shows through the overall mean, 3.904. Likewise, all the indicators were interpreted “agree”. The indicator with the highest mean, 4.28, shows that parents agree that applying fluoride to teeth preserves the minerals and guards against cavities.

Also, the lowest mean, 3.53, show that parents still agree that “wearing bite splints is necessary when I grind my teeth while sleeping.” Further in table 3, it shows that all parents agree to all stated indicators. These imply that parents are aware that dental health knowledge is a factor that affects their oral health practices.

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Oral Hygiene Practices

Table 3 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along oral hygiene practices.

Table 3 presents that the oral hygiene practices is factor affecting oral health practices of preschool children with the overall mean, 4.163 interpreted as “agree”. Further, it can be easily noticed that all the indicators got a mean which were interpreted as “agree”. This only shows that the parents agree to the fact that oral hygiene practices affect the oral health practices among parents of preschool children.

Table 3. Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Oral Hygiene Practices

<i>Indicator Statements</i>	<i>Mean Interpretation</i>	
<i>B. Oral Hygiene Practices</i>		
1. I know that I should change my toothbrush every after three to four months (Alam ko na dapat palitan ang aking sipilyo tuwing pagkatapos ng tatlo hanggang apat na buwan)	4.01	Agree
2. I know that I should soak my toothbrush in anti-bacterial mouthwash for 30 seconds. (Alam ko na dapat kong ibabad ang aking sipilyo sa anti-bacterial mouthwash sa loob ng tatlumpong Segundo)	4.17	Agree
3. I know that I should brush gently my teeth using small, circular motion. (Alam ko na dapat akong magsipilyo ng marahan gamit ang maliit at pabilog na galaw)	4.34	Agree
4. I know that I should use fluorinated toothpaste. (Alam ko nan a dapat akong gumamit ng fluorinated toothpaste.)	4.12	Agree
5. I know that I should brush my tongue. (Alam ko na dapat kong linisan ang aking dila)	4.15	Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean 4.163	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

The highest mean, 4.34, shows that parents know that they should brush gently their teeth using small, circular motion. This implies that parents are aware of oral hygiene practices and that these factors highly affect their oral health practices.

The identified lowest mean, 4.01, show that parents still agree that they should change toothbrush every after three to four months. Further in table 3, it shows that all parents agree to all stated indicators. These imply that parents are aware that oral hygiene practices are factors that affect their oral health practices.

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Dietary Habits

Table 4 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along dietary habits.

Table 4. Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Dietary Habits

<i>Indicator Statements</i>	<i>Mean Interpretation</i>	
<i>C. Dietary Habits</i>		
1. I know that retention of sweet food on my child’s teeth can lead to tooth decay. (Alam ko na ang pagpapanatili ng matamis na pagkain sa ngipin ng aking anak ay maaaring humantong sa pagkabulok ng ngipin)	4.35	Agree
2. I know that avoiding carbonated drinks will help prevent tooth decay. (Alam ko na ang pag-iwas sa mga carbonated na inumin ay makakatulong na maiwasan ang pagkabulok ng ngipin)	3.98	Agree
3. I know that avoiding alcohol and tobacco use will reduce my chance of getting oral cancer. (Alam ko na ang pag-iwas sa alcohol at paggamit ng tabako ay makakabawas sa aking pagkakataong magkaroon ng kanser sa bibig)	4.20	Agree
4. I know that often drinking of coffee and tea will cause a chip and discolor to one’s teeth. (Alam ko na ang madalas nap ag-inom ng kape at tsaa ay magdudulot ng tipak at pag-iba ng kulay sa ngipin)	4.06	Agree
5. I know that eating lean sources of protein such as skinless poultry and fish is good for dental health. (Alam ko na ang pagkain ng protina ng walang balat na manok at isda ay Mabuti para sa kalusugan ng ngipin)	3.93	Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean 4.106	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

Table 4 shows that the dietary habits are a factor affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. The overall

mean, 4.106 shows that parents agree to this. In particular among the indicators with the highest mean, “the parents’ knowledge on the retention of sweet food on their child’s teeth can lead to tooth decay,” 4.35 mean, only shows that the parents highly agree that their dietary habits can affect the oral health.

Also, the lowest mean, 3.93, show that parents still agree that “eating lean sources of protein such as skinless poultry and fish is good for dental health.” Further in table 4, it shows that all parents agree to all stated indicators. These imply that parents are aware that dietary habits are a factor that affects their oral health practices.

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Access to Dental Health

Table 5 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along access to dental health.

Table 5. *Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Access to Dental Health*

<i>Indicator Statements</i>	<i>Mean Interpretation</i>	
D. Access to Dental Health		
I know that dental health care facility is accessible in my community. (Alam ko na ang pasilidad ng pangangalaga sa kalusugan ng ngipin ay madaling mapuntahan sa aking komunidad)	3.98	Agree
I know that some health insurance does not cover dental health care. (Alam ko na ang ibang mga health insurance ay hindi saklaw ang pangangalaga sa kalusugan ng ngipin)	3.58	Agree
I know that dental health care procedures are quite expensive. (Alam ko na ang mga iba’t ibang proseso sa pangangalaga ng ngipin ay may kamahalan)	4.11	Agree
I know that the number of dentists on duty are limited. (Alam ko na limitado lamang ang bilang ng mga dentista na nasa trabaho)	3.77	Agree
I know that free dental hygiene kits are available on dental health care facilities. (Alam ko na ang mga libreng dental hygiene kit ay makukuha sa mga pasilidad ng pangangalaga sa kalusugan ng ngipin)	3.86	Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean 3.865	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

Table 5 shows that access to dental health is a factor affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. The overall mean, 3.865 is interpreted agree. This means that parents highly agree that access to dental health highly affects their oral health practices.

The indicator with the highest mean, 4.11, “parents know that dental health care procedures are quite expensive,” show that parents identified and agreed that this highly affects their oral health practices. The lowest mean, 3.58 indicates that parents know that some healthcare insurance does not cover dental health care. They have considered this still as a high factor that affects their oral health practices.

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Parental Attitudes and Beliefs

Table 6 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along parental attitudes and beliefs.

Table 6. *Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Parental Attitudes and Beliefs*

<i>Indicator Statements</i>	<i>Mean Interpretation</i>	
E. Parental Attitudes and Beliefs		
1. I believe that opening or tearing off tags will make my teeth stronger. (Naniniwala ako na ang pagbukas o pagtanggap ng mga tag ay magpapatibay ng aking mga ngipin)	3.54	Agree
2. I believe that yellow color teeth are actually stronger than pearly white teeth. (Naniniwala ako na ang dilaw na kulay ng mga ngipin ay mas matibay kaysa sa mala-perlas na putting ngipin)	3.68	Agree
3. I believe that my permanent chip teeth have the ability to regrow. (Naniniwala ako na ang aking mga permanenteng ngipin na nabawasan ay may kakayahang tumubo ulit)	3.33	Neutral
4. I believe that placing a medical plant cloves in my decayed tooth will help me relieve pain. (Naniniwala ako na ang paglalagay ng halamang medical na cloves sa aking nabubulok na ngipin ay makakatulong na mapawi ang sakit)	3.57	Agree
5. I believe that dental cleaning will cause loosening of my teeth. (Naniniwala ako na ang paglilinis ng aking ngipin ay magdudulot ng pagluwag sa aking ngipin)	3.36	Neutral
	Overall Weighted Mean 3.498	Neutral

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

Table 6 shows that parents find it neutral or that is neither they agree or disagree that parental attitudes and beliefs affect the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. The overall mean, 3.498 is interpreted “neutral.” This shows that parents either agree or disagree with parental attitudes and beliefs affect their oral health practices.

Also, the indicator with the lowest mean, 3.33, show that parents neither believe or not that permanent chip teeth have the ability to regrow. Further in table 6, the indicator with 3.36 mean, stating that dental cleaning would cause loosening of their teeth shows that parents still neither agree nor disagree and that dietary habits moderately affects their oral health practices.

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Cultural Influences

Table 7 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along cultural influences.

Table 7 shows that parents find it neutral or that is neither they agree or disagree that cultural influences affect the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. The overall mean, 3.221 is interpreted “neutral.” This shows that parents either agree or disagree with cultural influences to be affecting their oral health practices.

The highest mean, 3.46, show that parents neither believe or do not believe that their permanent chip teeth have the ability to regrow. This indicator shows that cultural influences of parents moderately affects their oral health practices. All indicators in table 7 are interpreted neutral. These imply that parents agree that cultural influences are factors that moderately affects their oral health practices.

Table 7. Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Cultural Influences

<i>Indicator Statements</i>	<i>Mean Interpretation</i>	
F. Cultural Influences		
1. I believe that traditional remedies such as use of cotton ball soaked in aspirin helps relieve pain (Naniniwala ako na ang mga tradisyonal na remedyo tulad ng paggamit ng bulak na ibinabad sa aspirin ay nakakatulong na mapawi ang sakit)	3.44	Neutral
2. I believe that my permanent chip teeth have the ability to regrow. (Naniniwala ako na ang aking mga permanenteng ngipin na nabawasan ay may kakayahang tumubo ulit)	3.46	Neutral
3. I believe that dental treatment should be avoided during early age. (Naniniwala ako na ang pagpapagamot sa ngipin ay dapat iwasan sa murang edad)	3.29	Neutral
4. I believe that chewing betelnut or nganga will kill bacteria in my mouth. (Naniniwala ako na ang pangnguya ng betelnut o nganga ay makakatulong sa pagpatay ng bakteryang sa aking bibig)	3.18	Neutral
5. I believe that I am not allowed to have tooth extraction even if my teeth are decaying. (Naniniwala ako na bawal akong magpabunot ng ngipin kahit nabubulok na ang aking ngipin)	2.71	Neutral
Overall Weighted Mean	3.221	Neutral

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Education and Awareness

Table 8 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along access to education and awareness.

Table 8. Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Education and Awareness

<i>Indicator Statements</i>	<i>Mean Interpretation</i>	
G. Education and Awareness		
1. I am aware that I need to brush my teeth for 2-3 minutes at least twice a day. (Alam ko na kailangan kong magsipilyo ng ngipin dalawa hanggang tatlong minute dalawang beses sa isang araw)	4.07	Agree
2. I am aware that using soft fine bristle toothbrush won't harm or irritate my gums. (Alam ko na ang paggamit ng malambot na sipilyo ay hindi makakasama o makakairita sa aking galagid)	4.12	Agree
3. I am aware that I should not share my toothbrush with anyone else in my family. (Alam ko na hindi ko dapat ibahagi ang aking sipilyo sa sinuman sa aking pamilya)	4.23	Agree
4. I am aware that I must attend to dental lectures and campaign programs on dental health. (Alam ko na dapat akong dumalo sa mga dental lecture at programa sa kalusugan sa ngipin)	4.27	Agree
5. I am aware that dental cleaning and check-up must be done at early age. (Alam ko na ang paglilinis at pagpapakonsulta ng ngipin ay dapat gawin sa murang edad)	4.03	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.150	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

Table 8 shows that education and awareness is a factor affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. The overall mean, 4.150 is interpreted agree. This means that parents agree that education and awareness affect their oral health practices.

The highest mean, 4.27, shows that parents are aware that they must attend to dental lectures and campaign programs on dental health.

Also, the lowest mean, 4.03, shows that parents are aware that dental cleaning and check-up must be done at early age. Further, all indicators in table 8 have a mean interpreted as “agree.” These results imply that parents agree that education and awareness is a factor that highly affects their oral health practices.

Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Collaboration with Healthcare Providers

Table 9 shows the extent of factors affecting the oral health practices of preschool children along collaboration with healthcare providers.

Table 9 shows that collaboration with healthcare providers is a factor affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children. The overall mean, 4.074 is interpreted agree. This means that parents agree that collaboration with healthcare providers affects their oral health practices.

The highest mean, 4.25, shows that parents are aware that they should attend together with their child in a fun creative activity about oral health practices.

Table 9. Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children Along Collaboration with Healthcare Providers

Indicator Statements	Mean Interpretation	
<i>H. Collaboration with Healthcare Providers</i>		
1. I am aware that my dentist has demonstrated to me the proper interdental cleaning within the dental setting. (Alam ko na ipinakita sa akin ng aking dentista ang wastong paglilinis ng interdental sa loob ng klinika)	4.22	Agree
2. I am aware that teachers in my child’s school are supporting health diet for a healthier tooth. (Alam kong sinusupportahan ng mga guro sa paaralan ng aking aking anak ang tamang pagkain para sa malusog na mga ngipin)	4.23	Agree
3. I am aware that I should attend together with my child in a fun creative activity about oral health practices. (Alam ko na dapat akong dumalo kasama ang aking anak sa isang masayang malikhain aktibidad tungkol sa mga kasanayan sa kalusugan ng bibig)	4.25	Agree
4. I am aware that I should bring my child to dentist once the first tooth of my child comes. (Alam kong dapat kong dalhin ang aking anak sa dentista kapag tumubo ang unang ngipin)	3.71	Agree
5. I am aware that I should consult my child’s pediatrician and dentist when my child’s gum is bleeding. (Alam kong dapat kong komunsulta sa pediatrician at dentista ng aking anak kapag dumudugo ang galagid ng aking anak)	3.94	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean		4.074
		Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree (Malakas na umaayon); 3.50-4.49, Agree (Umaayon); 2.50-3.49, Neutral (Maaaring umaayon o di umaayon); 1.50-2.49, Disagree (Di ummayon); 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree (Malakas na di umaayon)

Also, the lowest mean, 3.71, shows that parents are aware that they should bring their child to dentist once the first tooth of their child comes. Further, all indicators in table 9 have a mean interpreted as “agree.” These results imply that parents agree that collaboration with healthcare providers is a factor that highly affects their oral health practices.

Relationships between the Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children and the Respondents’ Profile Variables

Table 10 below presents the Pearson r Coefficients of Correlations between extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschool children and the respondents’ profile variables.

Table 10 presents the computed r-values for sex and the factors: dental health, parental attitudes and beliefs, and cultural influences as .141, .249, .155 and .180 yielded a .033, .000, .037, and .018 respectively. The significant level of the Pearson r coefficient of correlations is below the significance level of 0.05 set at the start of this study. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states, “There is no significant relationship between the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschoolers across their profile variables,” is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between these factors affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children and the respondents’ profile variable sex. Thus, there is an indicated association between the variables.

Likewise, with respect to age, the computed r-value for dental health, dietary habits, parental attitudes and beliefs, and the cultural influences are -.139, .184, -.271, and -.207 and yielded a .035, .005, .000, and .002 respectively. The level of significance indicates that there is a relationship that exists between the between the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschoolers across their profile variable, age. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the dental health, dietary habits, parental attitudes and beliefs, and the cultural influences with the age of the respondents.

Also, with respect to highest educational attainment, the computed r-value for oral hygiene, dietary habits, parental attitudes and beliefs,

and cultural influences are .161, .284, -.179, and -.341 and yielded a .014, .000, .007, and .000 respectively. The level of significance indicates that there is a relationship that exists between the between the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschoolers across their profile variable, highest educational attainment. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the oral hygiene, dietary habits, parental attitudes and beliefs, and cultural influences with the highest educational attainment of the respondents.

Further, with respect to income, the computed r-value for dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, and cultural influences are .228, .143, .225, and -.225 have yielded a .010, .031, .001, and .000 respectively. The level of significance indicates that there is a relationship that exists between the between the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschoolers across their profile variable, income. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, and cultural influences with the income of the respondents.

Table 10. *Relationships between the Extent of Factors Affecting Oral Health Practices Among Parents of Preschool Children and the Respondents' Profile Variables*

Independent Variables	Pearson Correlation	Dental Health	Oral Hygiene	Dietary Habits	Parental Attitudes & Beliefs	Cultural Influences	Education & Awareness
Sex	r-Value	.141*	-.006	-.018	.249**	.155*	.015
	Sig	.033	.930	.784	.000	.018	.825
Age	r-Value	-.139*	-.025	.184**	-.271**	-.207**	-.068
	Sig	.035	.707	.005	.000	.002	.303
Highest Educational Attainment	r-Value	.125	.161*	.284**	-.179**	-.341**	.129
	Sig	.058	.014	.000	.007	.000	.050
Income	r-Value	.228**	.143*	.225**	-.075	-.255**	-.014
	Sig	.000	.031	.001	.257	.000	.837
Number of Family Members	r-Value	-.118	-.143*	.037	-.012	-.089	-.180**
	Sig	.073	.031	.579	.852	.180	.006

*Significant at 0.05 level **Significant at 0.01 level

Furthermore, with respect to number of family members, the computed r-value for oral hygiene, and education and awareness are -.143, and -.180 and have yielded a .031, and .006 respectively. The level of significance indicates that there is a relationship that exists between the between the extent of factors affecting oral health practices among parents of preschoolers across their profile variable, number of family members. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the oral hygiene, and education and awareness with the number of family members of the respondents.

The results show that in terms of sex, age, highest educational attainment, income, and number of family members have significant relationships to the factors affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children particularly on dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, parental attitudes and beliefs, cultural influences, and education and awareness. It implies that these profile variables of the respondents have an indicated association to the factors affecting oral health practices which need to be addressed to improve the oral health practices of parents which will redound to their children.

Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from the salient findings are as follows: The profile variables of parents, especially their educational attainment, income, and number of family members, are crucial and need utmost attention. Factors affecting oral health practices are directed towards dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, education and awareness, and collaboration with healthcare providers. There is a significant relationship between the factors affecting the oral health practices among parents of preschool children and the respondents' profile variables, particularly in terms of dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, parental attitudes and beliefs, cultural influences, education and awareness, and the profile variables of sex, age, highest educational attainment, income, and number of family members. Based on these findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are forwarded: Focus on the parents' profiles that need the most attention to improve oral health practices. Address the factors affecting oral health practices, such as dental health, oral hygiene, dietary habits, education and awareness, and collaboration with healthcare providers. Additionally, there should be orientation or focus group discussions with parents to improve oral health, particularly on the identified factors affecting their practices.

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